

Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage

Survey - Data report and reflections on the results 2021

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Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH)

Survey Data - Digital ICH Observatory

Filomena Sousa

Between May and June 2020, the DIGITAL ICH Observatory conducted the survey "Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH)". With this data we intended to analyse the practices and opinions of users of ICH Inventories.

The 2003 UNESCO Convention underlines the importance of ICH inventories to safeguard, disseminate, and raise awareness on ICH. All nominations for inscription in the ICH World Lists must be included on an ICH Inventory. Mostly for this reason, in the last 12 years, multiple processes of inventory have begun. Nevertheless, how are ICH inventories being used? How do users consult them? What opinion do they have about them? To answer these and other questions we applied this survey. Now we present the results of this work, starting by describing the sample studied in the research.

Sample Characterisation

95,9% Academic degree
4,1% High school

246 individuals responded to the survey, 61,8% women and 38,2% men. The majority are aged 41-60 (54,9%), but also answered the questionnaire the age groups 21-40 (28%) and 61+ (17,1%) (figs. 1-2). About 96% of individuals have an academic degree (associate, bachelor, master, or doctoral) and 87,4% are employed. Only 4,1% are studying, 8,1% are retired, and 0,4% are unemployed (fig. 3-4). 71,1% of respondents reside in an urban area and 28,9% in a rural area (fig.5).

Fig. 6 - Relation to Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH).

Among respondents, 78% refer that they relate to Intangible Cultural Heritage because they work or study on this subject; 14,3% are ICH practitioners, and 7,7% are just curious about ICH issues (not practising, working, or studying on ICH)¹ (fig.6).

Fig. 7 - Entity of work.

Figs. 1,2,3,4,5 - Sex, age, school qualification, activity and residence.

¹ In this question, respondents could only choose one option. For instance, if they studied on ICH and were also practitioners, they had to select the item that best characterised their present situation, the one with which they most identified.

Considering the respondents who work, about 88,8% are in public administration or education, science and culture services, performing intellectual and scientific professions (65,1%) or working in administrative (19,1%) or technical functions (10,6%). Only 4,7% are entrepreneurs, and 0,5% have no professional qualification. 42,2% work at the State (national administration - 25,4% - regional or local administration - 16,8%); 24,1% work at universities and research centres; 21,6% at NGOs and 12,1% at the private sector (fig.7).

Fig. 8 - World Region

Concerning geographic distribution, there is a higher Europe representation of respondents (70,7%), followed by Asia and the Pacific (13,4%), Africa (7,7%), the Latin America and the Caribbean region (6,5%) and, lastly, the Arab States (1,7%) (fig.8).

Sample Process

The sampling process was based on the non-probabilistic Snowball technique and data collection was carried out online, i.e., the survey link (Google forms) was sent to an international mailing list of about 1000 individuals² related to Intangible Cultural Heritage (researchers, practitioners, students, representatives of communities, professionals who work at State entities, at NGOs and other institutions). The questionnaire was also disseminated by social media, namely Facebook, newsletters and websites. All contacts were informed that they could spread the survey among their relevant contacts (related to ICH).

Sample critique

With the Snowball technique, which does not allow results generalisation, we only can describe the outcomes considering the sample, and because we do not know precisely how many people received the survey, we cannot calculate the response rate. However, on the one hand, on a theoretical exercise, considering the first 1000 contacts and the 246 responses we have a satisfactory rate of 24,6% (considering that the average of return for online surveys is 5%-30%).³ We can also consider 246 respondents a reasonable number to support the planned data analysis - a descriptive analysis restricted to the sample without extrapolation to the universe (individuals related to ICH). On the other hand,

² Mailing list built in the last ten years by the NGO Memória Imaterial through contacts with other ICH NGOs, UNESCO, nominations for World Lists, entities producing ICH Inventories, representative communities and others. The survey was anonymous, no identity information was requested, respondents were informed that the data collected would only be used for statistical treatment. The filling time was, on average, less than 15 minutes.

³ <https://www.customerthermometer.com/customer-surveys/average-survey-response-rate/>; <https://surveyanyplace.com/average-survey-response-rate/>; <https://surveysparrow.com/blog/what-is-a-good-survey-response-rate-indeed-heres-the-answer-we-found/> [consulted 25-06-2020].

since it is not possible to define the exact number of people who, worldwide, are related to ICH, the limitations of a non-probabilistic sample must be put into perspective. In the absence of accurate data about this population, it will be impossible to guarantee a representative sample, even if we used a random process.

Considering the main characteristics of the sample, we can assume that the sampling has some bias: the majority of the respondents are European, with higher education, working as professionals or specialists in the field of social science, culture and ICH. However, if we look to the context of the ICH processes (not to the cultural practices but the patrimonialization process) the bias already exists in the "real world". We think that the sample represents those who, nowadays, are actually related to ICH's patrimonialization processes: individuals who are familiar with the concept of ICH, the 2003 UNESCO Convention and the UNESCO recommendations - the European experts and professionals that contributed to the Convention construction and its implementation (see graphics.1 and 2, page 6).

About the higher European representation, we come across it in different aspects of the ICH processes: the largest number of national e-Inventories are European (Sousa, 2017); a significant amount of elements registered in the Representative List are from Europe; a considerable number of ICH NGOs accredited by UNESCO are European, among other aspects.

However, it is crucial that we are aware of this bias - the Europe-centric view in ICH's patrimonialization processes -, and since we will try to understand the involvement of different individuals, groups and communities in these processes, we consider convenient, for some analysis, to recode the variables "Region" and "Relation to ICH". So, to slightly increase their statistical relevance and the possibility to better characterise them, the "other regions" of the world will be recoded as a whole (fig.9), and "ICH practitioners and curious about ICH" will also be aggregated in a single category (fig.10).

Fig. 9 - World Region recoded.

Fig. 10 - Relation to ICH recoded.

About the two recoded variables, we can find slight differences when compared with the general sample. Analysing "practitioners/curious about ICH" and those "who work/study on ICH", there is a higher percentage of residents in rural areas among the first group (53,7% versus 21,9%). It is also among those who practice ICH that there is a higher percentage of workers in "administrative and technical functions" (44,5% compared to 26,3%) and less "intellectual and scientific professions" (37,8% versus 71,6%). This group is also characterised by more employees in the "private sector" (34,8%) and "retired" people (18,5%) (table.1).

		Rural residence	Adm + Tech	Intellect. scientific	Private Sector	Retired
Relation to ICH	Practice ICH + Curious	53,7%	44,5%	37,8%	34,8%	18,5%
	Work or study on ICH	21,9%	26,3%	71,6%	6,5%	5,2%

Table 1 - Relation to ICH recoded/rural residence/profession/work entity and

Regarding the "Region", the most distinctive characteristic seems to be a higher percentage of men respondents in "Other Regions" (56,9% compared to 30,5% in "Europe and North America Region"), there is also a slight increase of "urban residents" in those regions (88,9% versus 63,8%) (table.2).

		Sex Male	Urban residence
Region	Other Regions	56,9%	88,9%
	Europe and North America Region	30,5%	63,8%

Table 2 - Region/male/urban residence

The structure of the survey

The study of practices and opinions of ICH Inventories' users.

After the sociodemographic characterization, the survey addressed three other groups of questions: one relating ICH Inventories and the knowledge on the UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage; a group about the practices of ICH inventories' users - number of inventories consulted; the regularity and time spent on these inventories; inventories' characteristics and types of use (search, content, social networks, types of "interaction"/participation); and finally, the third group on opinions - inventories' evaluation; opinion on the importance of inventories in ICH safeguarding; opinion on what inventories should contain, how they should be structured and how communities, groups or individuals (CGIs) should participate in them.⁴

Practices - ICH Inventories and 2003 UNESCO Convention.

About relation to ICH inventories, 90% of those who "work or study on ICH" have already worked on ICH inventories. This group is very familiar with the 2003 UNESCO Convention, 88% "know well or very well" this document (graphic.1). They consult inventories at least once a month, for one or more hours and most of them know 5 to 10 or more inventories.

Among "ICH practitioners and curious about ICH", 48,1% "don't know or badly know" the 2003 UNESCO Convention (graphic.1). Among these, 53,8% have never consulted ICH inventories (graphic.2). If they did it, the frequency is once a year or even less, and for 5 to 30 minutes.

Graphic 1 - Relation to ICH * Do you know the 2003 UNESCO Convention?

⁴ Among the total respondents who have consulted at least one inventory (216).

Graphic 2 - Never consulted an ICH inventory * Relation to ICH * Do you know the 2003 UNESCO Convention?

These values converge to the hypothesis made on the bias that exists in the "world of ICH" - who have more information on ICH are the experts and professionals involved in the implementation of the Convention (see page 3). We cannot forget that the ICH concept was fostered by national and supranational governmental institutions and their experts. Through an etic procedure, these institutions defined legal instruments for the safeguarding of ICH, i.e., this process was not born out of populations' claims or their involvement in these decisions (Leal, 2013; Sousa, 2015). If the UNESCO and some States proclaim the need for direct participation of communities, groups and individual (CGIs) in these processes, in practice, the real involvement is still residual. It starts to be more significant, but much remains to be done to achieve this goal.

Practices - ICH inventories consulted (characterization).

Most frequently, respondents consult inventories in their language (55,6%), in second place are inventories consulted in English (41,2%). Only 3,2% are in other languages, different from English or mother tongue (fig.11).

The majority of inventories consulted have a national scope (55,6%), 19,9% are transnational, having ICH elements from several countries; 17,1% have a regional focus and 7,4% are local (fig. 12).

Most of these inventories have elements from the 5 ICH domains (52,8%), but 15,3% are exclusively dedicated to "social practices, rituals and festive events"; 11,1% to "traditional craftsmanship"; 8,8% to "oral expressions", also 8,8% to "performing arts" and only 3,2% are dedicated to "knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe" (fig. 13). Most of these inventories have up to 50 inscribed elements (52,9%).

The States promotes 49,1% of the inventories consulted - 34,7% with national management and 14,4% have regional administration -, NGOs promote 25,9% inventories and UNESCO promotes 13,4%. Private individuals promote only 0,5%, and 6,7% are managed by other types of organisations (fig. 14).

In my country's language 55,6%

Figs.11 IHC Inventories' language

55,6% National

Figs.12 IHC Inventories' Geographic level

Inventories consulted: 52.8% about all ICH domains

Fig. 13 - ICH domains in Inventories

Fig. 14 - The Inventory Promoter

Respondents also report that most of the inventories consulted are public (87%), online (79,6%) and open access (73,1%) - what we denominate as "ICH e-Inventories" (Sousa, 2017). Most consider these inventories updated (53,7%), 30% do not know if they are updated, and 17,1% say they are not. The majority do not know if inventories make calls for people's participation or think they do not make it at all (57,4%).

Considering all this characterization and the variable "Relation to ICH", we find two differences comparing those "who work/study on ICH" and "practitioners/curious about ICH": a) the first group consulted more inventories dedicated to all ICH domains and the second group consulted more inventories considering a specific ICH domain - 76,3% versus 41% (graphic.3) (with special incidence in "traditional craftsmanship" and "oral expressions" for the second group); 2) it is also among those who practice ICH that the majority of inventories consulted is not promoted by the States, but by NGOs and other organizations (55,3% versus 44,4%) (graphic.4).

In relation to the "Region", there is a higher number of consulted inventories that are not online in "Other regions" than in "Europe and North America" (32,8% versus 11,2%) (graphic.5).

Graphic 3 - Relation to ICH * ICH Domains on consulted inventories

Graphic 4 - Relation to ICH * Promoters of consulted inventories

Graphic 5 - Region * Inventories consulted online

Evaluation - ICH inventories consulted.

To finish the consulted inventories' characterization, we asked respondents to rate these inventories on a scale between "very bad" and "very good". The results show that, in general, appreciation is positive, standing between "reasonable" (48,1%) and "good" (41,7%). Few people rate the inventories as "bad" (1,4%), and no one considers them "very bad". But also few rate them as "very good" (8,8%), that is, as exemplars (graphic.6).

Graphic 6 – Evaluation of ICH Inventories consulted.

Practices - ICH inventories' types of uses.

Considering how respondents consult inventories, 23 variables were analysed - a range of practices, such as "read texts"; "watch videos", "visit only the front page" of the inventory, "explore multiple pages", "explore by search", "share info on social media", "leave comments", etc. (see questions 24-28 Annex A). For each item, the respondent mentioned the frequency with which he performed these practices: "Never", "Rarely", "Sometimes", "Many times" or "Always".⁵

The results show that, regardless the type of relationship with ICH or sociodemographic data, the majority of individuals (more than 60%) navigate "always or many times" through multiple pages of the inventory, reading information and seeing photos of ICH elements (over 70%). The frequency with which they watch videos or hear soundtracks, being high, decreases slightly compared to the frequency of reading and seeing photos (graphic.7).

Over 60% of respondents say that it is common to know what they are looking for when they consult an ICH inventory. Among those who use the search, about 50% say that "many times or always" use the "simple search", by keyword. "Advanced searches", by location, domain or other criteria, are frequent but decrease compared to "simple search" (referred by 30% to 40% of respondents) (graphic.7).

It should be noted that, despite the frequent browse by inventories' multiple pages (as mentioned above), about 20% of respondents only visit the first page of the inventories, not exploring their contents.

⁵ To increase the statistical relevance, the categories of these variables were recoded in "Never or rarely" (aggregation of "Never" and "Rarely"); "Sometimes" and "Many times or always" (aggregation of "Many times" and "Always").

Graphic 7 - Most frequent practices when consulting an ICH inventory. (Carried out "many times or always" - Variables 24-28).

Considering the other extreme of the frequency scale, we find that respondents rarely "interact" on the inventory platforms or share information consulted on social networks: 50% to 70% of respondents "never or rarely" make comments, leave questions, collaborate in forums, subscribe to "communities" or propose content. Participation through the subscription of newsletters, being equally rare, is a little more frequent. It is also rare to share inventories' information on respondents' social networks or to use the social networks of inventory promoters (graphic.8).

Graphic 8 – Less frequent practices when consulting an ICH inventory. (Carried out "never or rarely" – Variables 26 and 28).

Opinion - ICH inventories' structure and utility.

As already mentioned, in order to understand not only the practices but also the representations on ICH inventorying process, in the last part of the survey, we asked respondents to give their opinion on the importance of inventories in ICH safeguarding; on what information inventories should contain, how they should be structured and how communities, groups or individuals should participate in them. To obtain this opinion, we used the following scale of importance: "Not Important", "Less important", "So-so", "Important", "Very important" and "No opinion".⁶

⁶ To increase the statistical relevance, the categories of these variables were recoded in "Not Important or less important" (aggregation of "Not Important", "Less important" and "So, So"); "Important" and "Very important". In justified situations, the categories "Important" and "Very important" were also added. "No opinion" percentages were very residual and were considered "Missing cases".

Starting with the analysis on opinions about the theme above mentioned - the way respondents "interact" with inventories - it is curious to find a discrepancy between practices and representations. What respondents do differ from what they value. For example, on the one hand, they rarely participate in forums, subscribe communities or use social networks associated with inventories. On the other hand, the majority (between 50% and 85%) consider "important or very important" that the inventories have "contents to share" (84,6%), a "presence on social networks" (75,8%), be "interactive" (75,8%), promote "forums and communities" (64,9%) and provide a "newsletter" (57,3%) (graphic.9).

Graphic 9 – Opinion: What should an ICH inventory have/How should an inventory be? (Variables 33.3 to 33.7 and 32.3)

The discrepancy between practices and opinions can be interpreted in multiple ways. Still, two hypotheses seem evident: respondents value this participation, but the inventories do not provide the necessary tools to achieve it; or respondents theoretically value something that, in practice, they are not available to do ("do what I say, don't do what I do").

The survey results do not allow us to test these hypotheses, this is definitely an issue to develop in future researches. However, if we consider data from the Digital ICH Observatory, and the ICH e-Inventories study (Sousa, 2017), we see that, in 2017, the percentage of inventories that promoted active user interaction was small. For instance, on the use of social networks, in 158 inventories analysed, more than 70% had no presence on social networks. Only 27% had project pages in social media, mostly on Facebook and on Twitter. Of these, only 23% shared videos on YouTube, and only 21% shared photos on Instagram. We can also see that only 12% allowed visitors to share content on their profiles, once again, mostly on Facebook and on Twitter.

Regarding generic characteristics of ICH inventories, practices and representations are more consistent. For instance, as already mentioned, respondents report that most of the inventories consulted are what we called "ICH e-Inventories" - public (87%), online (79,6%) and open access inventories (73,1 %). Analysing the opinions, we found that most of the respondents (60% to 70%) consider "very important" that inventories have these characteristics, that is, they should be public and available to all. They also value updated and searchable information (graphic.10).

Less valued seems to be the "entertaining" aspect of the inventory. Even when 80% to 90% of the respondents consider an "appealing design/layout" and "clear menus" to be essential (graphic.11), 75,5% do not value inventories because they are "funny" (graphic.10) or serve "to enjoy ICH" (graphic.12). Without advocating a total "scientific" attribute, too hermetic or difficult to consult, the practical side of inventories is, however, more valued than the recreational aspect (graphic.10).

Graphic 10 – Opinion: How should an ICH inventory be? (Variables 32)

Graphic 11 – Opinion: What should an ICH inventory have? (Variables 33.1 and 33.2)

Analysing the opinion on the importance of inventories, we found that the majority considers inventories "very important" as a measure to safeguard ICH (71,6%) (graphic.12). However, in line with the mentioned above, inventories are slightly more valued for their "technical" aspects than for their ability to increase practices. Observing the data, we have more respondents considering inventories "very important" "to provide information" (70,8%); "to give ICH visibility" (70,8%), "to archive ICH" (66,5%) than to "increase ICH practitioners" (49,8%) or "to engage people with ICH" (57,2%) (graphic.12).

Graphic 12 – Opinion: Why are ICH inventories important?

Opinion - ICH inventories' contents.

Regarding the contents that must be included in an ICH inventory, considering what respondents consider "very important", the majority (between 51% and 65%) finds the fields "tradition name" and "short description of the tradition" essential. Information that proves the "community consent" to make the inventory, and information that guarantees the "intellectual rights" associated with the ICH elements are also considered "very important" by most respondents (graphic.13).

More detailed and developed information is considered essential for 30% to 50% of respondents: specific information, for example, about ICH practitioners; details on the tradition, historical data, photos, videos, references to risks associated with the practice, a safeguard plan and information on the 2003 UNESCO Convention (graphic.13).

The availability of soundtracks and data on "methodology/team info" in the inventories, being considered important, are not considered as important as the aspects previously mentioned (graphic.13).

Analysing what respondents do not consider important to be in an ICH inventory, new technologies tools for ICH visualisation and fruition are not regarded as essential. For instance, 60% to 70% of the respondents do not give importance to "access to virtual reality/augmented reality", "streaming sessions"⁷ and "360° photos" (graphic.13).

Graphic 13 – Opinion: What information should be available in an ICH inventory?

⁷ This data was collected in 2019, before the COVID 19 pandemic, when the use of streaming sessions, webinars and other web systems were widely used for ICH-related initiatives. We hypothesise that these circumstances may have changed this opinion. However, we cannot confirm that.

Practices and Opinions - ICH inventories' participation.

As we saw before, 53,2% of respondents "never or rarely" propose content for inventories, 57,4% do not know if inventories open calls for participation. However, questioned about what characterises a "participatory inventory", the majority rates as "important or very important" "to use participatory techniques" (90,5%), "to have a call for contributions" (82,6%), "to provide technical support" (93%), "to be easy to fill" (90,5%), "to allow voluntary contributions" (82,6%), "to have moderators" (81,6%) and "to give instructions for contributions" (81,6%) (graphic.14a).

This result takes us back to the study on ICH e-Inventories (Sousa, 2017) which concludes that, among the 158 inventories analysed, the method of participation of the communities, groups and individuals in the inventory process is little detailed, only 22 inventories (14% of the total) announce in a visible way "the character of the collaborative process of inventory and call for the direct participation of the practitioners of cultural expressions, local institutions and other actors involved" (pp. 8).

Graphic 14a – Opinion: What is important in a participatory ICH inventory?

It is also curious to recall that users do not "interact" when navigating on ICH e-Inventories, but if we consider the participation in public actions about ICH inventories, the results are diverse. The majority of respondents (50% to 75%) have already participated in public sessions (71,8%), training actions (71,3%), assemblies (63,4%) and debates whose main subject was the ICH inventory (56,9%) (graphic.14b). On this point, we cannot forget the characteristics of the sample and the fact that 78% of respondents "work or study" in the field of intangible cultural heritage.

Graphic 14b – Participation in ICH public sessions, ICH plenaries and ICH capacity-building/Workshops.

Also related to participatory methodologies is a question about the role of communities, groups and individuals (CGIs) in the inventory processes. Results show that the participation of CGIs in different stages of the process is very well evaluated. However, most of the respondents (50% to 63%) see CGIs especially as "beneficiaries" of the process, or as actors who help "to identify ICH to inventory". Engaging communities, groups and individuals in decision-making or in the inventory management is not as valued as involving them as "informants" (graphic.15).⁸

Considering these results, and the different levels of CGIs engagement in ICH safeguarding (Sousa, 2018),⁹ we can say that respondents are more in line with an "Informative/advisory Level" of participation. It seems that they see CGIs "as beneficiaries and informants, or even as consultants, but without the possibility of deciding or influencing the defined plan". In this case, CGIs are mainly associated with "elementary levels of involvement" participating "for example, by attending information sessions, being interviewed and answering surveys or participating in focus groups" (pp.35).

In fact, almost one-third of the respondents considered that it is "not important or less important" that CGIs have an active role "to manage the inventory process" (33%). Some consider CGIs do not have an important role as advisers (21,3%) or to decide "what and how to inventory" (23%) (graphic.15). That is, "the ideal maximum level" of participation, a "mobilizer advanced level" is not yet unanimously valued. In a "mobilizer advanced level" the initiative of the inventory process begins with the CGIs, and they self-mobilize and manage the project (in partnership with external agents) (Sousa, 2018).

⁸ Whatever the relationship with the ICH or sociodemographic characteristics.

⁹ "Different levels of CGI involvement through the inventory process:

- a) Informative/Advisory Level - external agents define the problems to be solved and the solutions to be implemented, while considering the CGIs only as beneficiaries and informants, or even as consultants, but without the possibility of deciding or influencing the defined plan - for example, by attending information sessions, being interviewed and answering surveys or participating in focus groups. These are elementary levels of involvement;
- b) Advisory/Mobilizer basic level - the CGIs are part of forums, councils, panels or citizens' juries, working meetings and other group dynamics. In this situation they are considered as agents in the inventory process;
- c) Mobilizer basic level - if the collaboration materializes itself in a shared responsibility relationship, in a commitment through which they participate actively in the decisions made, the level of involvement is higher, and the CGIs present themselves as partners and co-authors of the planning. Participation increases if there is an effective implication in the various implementation phases - diagnosis, planning, action and evaluation;
- e) Mobilizer advanced level - the ideal maximum level is achieved when the initiative of the inventory process begins with the CGIs and when, in partnership with external agents, it is the communities, groups and individuals who self-mobilize and manage the project (Adnan et al., 1992; Community Places, 2014; Pretty, 1994)." (Sousa, 2018, pp. 35).

Graphic 15 – Opinion: What should be the role of communities, groups or individuals in ICH inventories?

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Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH)

Survey Data - Digital ICH Observatory

Reflections on the survey results: project designers' point-of-view

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1. Introduction

This paper reports some reflections on the survey *Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH)* results, seizing from our experience in designing, implementing and managing archives of (intangible) cultural heritage, from the point of view both of defining and structuring data and metadata, and of the usability of websites, making use of design methodologies and heuristic evaluation methods.

In recent years, the States that ratified the 2003 UNESCO Convention for the safeguarding of the intangible cultural heritage have faced the need to build archiving/inventory systems capable to involve all the stakeholders that contribute to the ICH safeguarding. Implementing and managing intangible cultural heritage inventories is a challenging activity involving different skills and competencies. Communities, with the help of ethnographers, social history experts, and other social scientists, identify which cultural heritage to include in the inventory. On the one hand, the structure of the catalogue metadata must be defined by experts who, starting from the comparison of different inventory methods in different countries, identify the best practices and define what kind of information to keep track of (ASPACI, 2011). All this essential and useful information for the safeguarding of the asset needs to be provided by the metadata structure defined. On the other hand, to disseminate and make available this intangible cultural heritage around the world, a suitable data model and multimodal search and visualization tools should be adopted, together with images, videos, and other multimedia that should be made available to users on the web.

The paper is structured as follows: In paragraph 2, after an overview of intangible heritage websites, with their characteristics and geographical distribution, a critical analysis of the survey results follows. Paragraph 3 discusses the outcomes of the website evaluation, in the framework of methodologies for defining websites and evaluation heuristics. Section 4 delves into the assessment of the survey results, starting from the data models used and the requirements of UNESCO in its Convention.

2. Characteristics of archives and inventories online

To better understand the outcome of the survey, in terms of the inventories consulted, we will begin with information regarding which inventories can be used, browsed, viewed and queried online.

On the UNESCO site itself,¹ a function for visualization and search of the items registered in its Lists is available. At present (beginning of 2021) there are 584 (registered) items corresponding to 131 Countries. All the items have an English version, regardless of their original language is.

¹ Dive into intangible cultural heritage! <https://ich.unesco.org/en/dive>

Since the ratification of the Convention by the States, many archives and inventories have been made available. To have an overall view of the available archives, since it is not so easy to locate them if one does not know them already, ICH mappings are available, such as Artese and Gagliardi (2015), or the one by Sousa (2017), which is constantly updated,² and which we used here. According to this work, 53% of inventories are located in Europe, 43% in other Regions and 4% in countries that have not yet ratified the 2003 Convention.³ This additional data helps discuss the survey findings, related to the 158 inventories of the 2017 report:

- inventories scope: 88 are national, 41 regional/local and 29 transnational ones;
- inventory promoters: 118 are under the custody of the States (75%); 20 are coordinated by Category2 UNESCO Centres, 12 inventories are promoted by NGOs, associations or foundations; 7 by National Commissions for UNESCO and 1 is developed under the individual title.

Severino and Venturini (2016) compare several national networks (of institutions, associations, and individuals) in France, Italy and Switzerland involved in the implementation of the 2003 UNESCO Convention to highlight national trends and specificities. Limited to the 3 states analysed, we can note that:

- Italy: The scope of online inventories is national (24.5% of nodes) and international (9%), while the majority is related to regional bodies, urban organizations, and also actors based in small villages (66.5%). Regarding promoters, institutional actors constitute 38% of nodes; several clusters of associations (43%) and clusters of individuals (19%) can be identified.
- France: national nodes account for 30%, local nodes for 65%, and international nodes for 5%. Institutions (45%) play the role of both authority and hub, ensuring the connection of the network, and associations (35%) and individuals (20%) constitute the remaining part.
- Switzerland: the distribution of local (62%) and national (32%) nodes represent the majority, leaving 6% to international players.

In analysing the survey, we have to take into account that, as already stated, the data reflect the views of the Western world because of the way respondents were enrolled. Based on the "ground truth" in mapping the archives and the languages in which these archives are available, the results of the survey are consistent with this data, along with the geographic origin of the respondents: 95% of the archives are accessed in their own language or English (fig. 1). The English language could be considered almost as a universal language in many scientific and humanistic fields.

In my country's language 55,6%

Figs.1 IHC Inventories' language

² <https://digitalich.memoriamedia.net/index.php/our-work/map>

³ According to the World Region recorded in the review.

Perhaps more surprising (from a statistical point of view), but understandable based on data taken more globally, is the fact that the number of people who query the archives in their own language is, in percentage, equal to those who query national archives (figs. 1 and 2). This can be explained considering the high percentage of national archives compared to all archives. Considering then globally, the national ‘scope’ (as national/regional/local) covers about 80% of the archives consulted, against 20% of the transnational archives. This data is in line with what was verified by Sousa (2017) and Severo and Venturini (2016).

55,6% National

Figs.2 IHC Inventories' Geographic level

Although the Convention identifies 5 categories of intangible heritage and almost all the inventories are created on this basis, others organize their data differently, either by inventorying data using more categories, e.g. Sahapedia⁴ adds ‘people’, ‘built spaces’ and so on, or by inventorying assets that belong only to one of the UNESCO categories (fig. 3).

Inventories consulted: 52.8% about all ICH domains

Fig. 3 - ICH domains in Inventories

⁴ <https://www.sahapedia.org/>

The creation and populating of inventories of intangible assets, as we have already said, requires transversal and multi/interdisciplinary skills: therefore, the work team, with specific skills and expertise, also requires long-term funding. Hence the fact that most archives are promoted by the State (through national or regional management), by NGOs, or by UNESCO, can be in line with the need to have good quality and up-to-date archives. However, since the number of inventories carried out by private entities, groups, communities or individuals is a minority, it is not possible to confirm this aspect.

The majority of the archives are public, online, and open access: these percentages are in agreement with the promoters of the archives, which in most cases are public bodies, NGOs, or UNESCO. Another of UNESCO's requests is that the inventories are kept up-to-date and in line with the communities that identify and recreate them: in line with these requests is the percentage of up-to-date archives.

As we have already seen, most of the archives are 'institutional', this aspect has a possible drawback: a lesser (or slower) openness towards social and public participation in the construction of the archives.

Analysing the results in detail, by user type and their knowledge of ICH, it can be seen that those who work or study ICH are more interested in archives that deal with all ICH domains (graphic 1), state promoters (graphic 2), and online (graphic 3). In general, we can say that these three characteristics are interrelated and could identify some large public archives. On the contrary, the ICH practitioners and the curious are more interested or attracted to archives on particular ICH domains, mainly managed by NGOs and available as static web pages. This could be the case, for example, of ACCU⁵, which concerns only “Performing arts”.

Graphic 1 - Relation to ICH * ICH Domains on consulted inventories

⁵ No longer available online, but only through the archive.org Wayback machine

Graphic 2 - Relation to ICH * Promoters of consulted inventories

Graphic 3 - Region * Inventories consulted online

3.Evaluation and use of ICH web sites

Every website is designed and implemented with users, purposes, and contexts of use in mind. The idea is to optimize the objective function for the user: the specific motivation that drives the user to enter a site and stay there, to fulfil his information needs. Also, web designers want to make the visit as pleasant as possible, possibly making the user come back again and again. Over the years, different methodologies have been developed for website design (Nielsen, 1997a), to create efficient and effective, data-intensive sites in specific domains, to:

- facilitate communication between different skills: designer, IT, end-user, domain expert, and so on;
- cope with a huge and ever-increasing amount of data, that may require finer and more selective ways of querying and visualizing it;
- effectively manage data that is interconnected; and
- deal with the entire life-cycle of the project.

Website evaluation has been the subject of numerous studies, especially in its early days. According to Jakob Nielsen (1997a), there are numerous aspects to take into account when designing and building websites. A more recent review of the evaluation methods can be found in Kabassi (2017), where the author compares different evaluation methods and models.

Heuristic criteria vary depending on the purpose of the site and the users it is intended to intercept and satisfy. Among the best known are the “Ten heuristics” of Jacob Nielsen (2020), or the high-level evaluation model by Polillo (2005), that identifies several criteria, namely: content, functionality, management, communication, usability, and accessibility. For museum-type or data-intensive sites, the quality of information, its completeness, and reliability are of overriding importance over other characteristics of playfulness and mobile friendliness. This also emerges in the section *Opinion - ICH inventories' structure and usefulness* (page 12) of the survey.

Besides, over the years, how users read and interact on the web has been analysed. According to a study by Nielsen Norman Group, originally carried out in 1997, and whose results were confirmed in 2020, users, on average, do not read, but “scan” the text in search of information of interest. This has greater value when the web pages consist of search engine results like Google or Duckduckgo. Other studies and statistics have evaluated the average time of permanence on the web pages, of bouncing, that represents the percentage of visitors who enter the site and then leave (“bounce”) rather than continuing to view other pages within the same site, and “dwell time” (how long site visitors spend on a web page). Results, valid above all for the home pages of the sites, indicate that the average permanence on web site pages is of approximately 15 seconds⁶ or not very long (“the average page visit lasts a little less than a minute”).⁷

In the survey, the evaluation of the inventories (see graphic 4) ranges from reasonable, corresponding to an average degree of satisfaction, to good and very good, with these positive evaluations reaching about 99% of the answers. Two aspects can explain this extremely positive evaluation: on the one hand, the ICH archives are extremely sectorial and, therefore, well-kept, with accurate and scientifically sound information, and are up-to-date. On the other hand, the users who took part in the survey are, for the most part, domain experts, so they are very interested in the content. Regarding respondents' use of websites, how they search and interact with websites and data - section *Practices - ICH inventories' types of uses-*, it can be seen that the interactions are performed in a more complex and prolonged manner than with standard sites. Users say they are more interested in

⁶ <https://www.crazyegg.com/blog/why-users-leave-a-website/>

⁷ <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/how-long-do-users-stay-on-web-pages/>

the content than average and, also, the percentage of people who say they see only one page (20%) is extremely low compared to standards. No statistics on bounce time percentages are available (to the best of our knowledge), except for specific examples, such as data on the Science Museum in London for which “dwell time is up 40% year-on-year and the overall bounce rate has reduced by 26%”⁸ and is of circa 60%.⁹

There are some useful considerations in understanding survey results:

- Websites related to intangible heritage are information-intensive, thus content-oriented rather than purely aesthetics-driven. Because they are mostly maintained by public entities (at the state, regional, or local level) or NGOs, the focus is primarily on the content (whether it be inventorying or simple lists of objects) and how to search and display results, as opposed to the “fashion” aspects of the interface.
- As mentioned above, the respondents are mostly people who work with ICH and its archives. So it is not surprising that they are interested in immersing themselves in the content, e.g., reading text, looking at photos and viewing multiple pages, very often when using websites.
- It is also interesting and shows a niche audience that more than half of the respondents, most of the time, know what they’re looking for, and search by keywords/domains, and other search keys.

Graphic 4 – Evaluation of ICH Inventories consulted.

Sharing content or links, participating in social media, subscribing to newsletters, and frequenting blogs and forums are all activities that have gained popularity in recent years: for these actions to be carried out properly, the website must offer relative functionality and users must be interested in performing them. The analysis shows that respondents are usually not interested in using these actions very often (lower half in graphic 5). These actions are the ones that are executed least frequently: ranging from 71% who never leave comments to 41% who don't share on their social media (see graphic 6). This behaviour appears to be in line with the respondents' roles, skills, and jobs, as well as their rather high average age (Fig 4).

⁸ <https://numiko.com/projects/science-museum-group/>

⁹ <https://www.similarweb.com/website/sciencemuseum.org.uk>

Graphic 5 - Most frequent practices when consulting an ICH inventory. (Carried out "many times or always" - Variables 24-28).

Graphic 6 – Less frequent practices when consulting an ICH inventory. (Carried out “never or rarely” – Variables 26 and 28).

Fig. 4 - Respondents – age.

4.Information and Data

Considering the results highlighted in Graphic 7 the most immediate comment is that among the elements with high percentages of *very important* we can find first of all those that could be expected, such as the “Tradition name” and the “Short description”, while the high results obtained by “Intellectual rights” or “Community consent” seem less obvious, the same being true for the high

values of *not important* or *less important* reported by tools related to new technologies, the last three of the graph.

By cross-referencing users' preferences about the elements considered most important with those considered least important, and taking into account UNESCO indications about ICH inventorying, an attempt can be made to extract a set of metadata useful to describe the necessary requirements for intangible heritage inventories. This is a field where a standard data model is yet far from being achieved, but the development of a common metadata model would allow global indexing of intangible assets coming from the various inventories. The main problem while achieving this is to find suitable models for expressing intangible cultural heritage and being able to meet the One-to-One Principle of Metadata (Miller, 2010), which is essential to distinguish digital copies from their physical source. Similar experiences have been faced in the field of museum data, such as the Smithsonian American Art Museum, whose data has been mapped successfully into the Europeana Data Model (EDM) and a new ontology has been introduced to extend the model (Szekely, 2013).

But the intangible cultural heritage is not a physical item collected by institutions, rather, it is a "living good" which exists in practice, evolving over time. According to the work of Wijesundara and Sugimoto (2018), this kind of heritage is performed during a given time and location, by different performers each time, and only once it has occurred, can the performance be captured by any medium. So resources are collected in the physical environment and further digitized to the digital space: each of these needs to be modelled by separated metadata and the CHDE model proposed by Wijesundara and Sugimoto meets these requirements and can describe both tangible and intangible cultural heritage information. The mapping between the model and the classes of existing ontologies together with the use of linked open data technologies make it possible to develop information systems capable of querying data from all inventories at the same time, as Europeana teaches us, and user preferences that emerged from the survey can address the choice about the information to keep and underline.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we have presented our reflections on the results of the survey *Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH)* based on our knowledge and experience in the definition, implementation, and management of intangible cultural heritage online inventories. The creation and periodic update of ICH inventories is a living, dynamic, permanent, bottom-up cultural process as defined by the UNESCO Convention 2003 and is an obligation of State Parties in the Conventions implementation process. To summarize, we can say that users are interested in archives whose content is related to their knowledge and geographic location. Their positive evaluation is very high, and they are more interested in the content than in the sharing and social media aspects.

These results could also provide us with new challenges for the definition of innovative methods and tools in management, search and visualization. Given the vast amount of data, how can we make it available, even to the general public? And if we could, would this be a problem for intangible cultural heritage? Would it put ICH at risk? Would it also put communities at risk?

Inventories of intangible assets should provide communities and various stakeholders with systematically organized and updated data, which is crucial for identifying and formulating appropriate safeguards and sustainable development measures.

Graphic 7 – Opinion: What information should be available in an ICH inventory?

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Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH)

Survey Data - Digital ICH Observatory

Digital Inventories: Structure, Usefulness, and Participation

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In this article we react to two chapters from the 2020 Inventories Survey, namely, "ICH inventories' structure and usefulness" and "ICH inventories' participation". We will discuss the answers of the respondents who took part in the quantitative survey "Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH)" visualised in graphics 9-10, 12 and 14-15 (Sousa, 2021),¹ give them meaning, and connect them to the experiences that we gained from the implementation of the 2003 UNESCO Convention in the Netherlands. The information that was gathered during this survey gives us an insight into how inventories are currently used and structured as well as what the - fulfilled and unfulfilled - expectations of the respondents are.

1. The inventory as stimulus and infrastructure for social networking

In regard to the questions "What should an ICH inventory have?" and "How should an inventory be?", we would like to discuss two aspects which are considered as "important" and "very important" by approximately 76% of the respondents; the first being the relationship between inventories and social networks and the second, the interactivity of the inventories (graphic 1).

Graphic 1 – Opinion: What should an ICH inventory have/How should an inventory be? (Variables 33.3 to 33.7 and 32.3)

¹ In this article - graphics 1,2,3,4 and 5. We will also refer to graphic 13 (Sousa, 2021) and graphic 6 in our text.

The category "presence on social networks", as it appears in the graphic, can be interpreted in diverse ways: general presence on social networks, presence on social networks originating from ICH practitioners, and presence on the social networks of the institutions that coordinate ICH inventories, such as the Dutch Centre for Intangible Cultural Heritage (DCIC) in the Netherlands. The category can also be approached in a more direct way and be understood as "the inventory as infrastructure for social networking". We wish to elaborate a little more on this last approach because, in our eyes, it has the potential to both strengthen existing safeguarding measures and inspire heritage professionals to be more proactive in that sense, if they haven't been already.²

Valdimar Hafstein draws attention to the fact that heritagisation can equate to recontextualisation when he writes: "To label a practice or a site as heritage is not so much a description [...] as it is an intervention. In fact, heritage reorders relations between persons and things, and among persons themselves, objectifying and recontextualizing them with reference to other sites and practices designated as heritage" (Hafstein, 2012, 508). The results of this recontextualisation process are visible in the (websites of the) inventories. It is unquestionable important to critically consider the inventories in light of the valuations and hierarchies created by heritage regimes (Bendix, 2014), that include as well as exclude specific forms of heritage, despite the adoption of the famous bottom-up principle of the 2003 UNESCO Convention and its corresponding emphasis on the involvement of the communities, groups, and individuals surrounding ICH (cf. Sousa, 2018, 13-16, 35-52). Nevertheless, understood as infrastructure, the inventories can give heritage bearers the opportunity to collaborate and exchange both good and bad experiences of safeguarding. Mutually beneficial exchange and cooperation can successfully be kick-started by taking a look at the inventory; especially if it offers the possibility to search by theme, "youth", "textile", "parade", and "urban" being some examples. Indeed, more than 90% of the respondents of the survey find searchability important or very important (graphic 2), even though it is not clear for which exact reason(s) they do.

In the Netherlands, the collaboration between the practitioners of several flower parades culminated in an inscription in the Dutch Register of Inspiring Examples of Safeguarding as well as in the creation of a general roadmap for collaborations amongst bearers of ICH. A digital version of this roadmap can be found on the website of the Register.³ Furthermore, practitioners of quite different forms of intangible heritage can help one another by reflecting on each other's heritage, sharing ideas, and developing creative projects together, once they have come into contact (Elpers, Verburg 2020, 38). For example, the practitioners of the Saint Martin celebration in the city of Utrecht⁴ have been sharing their experience regarding the creation of an international Saint Martin tourist route with a community in the village of Beesel who organises a yearly open-air spectacle based on the legend of Saint George and the Dragon.⁵

However, attention should also be drawn to the risks and challenges that come with collaborative projects: Do situations of competition arise between the bearers of diverse forms of heritage? Do

² Even though the respondents of the survey find social networks, interactivity, and forums important or very important, they have also answered that they rarely participate in anything.

³ <https://www.immaterieelerfgoed.nl/nl/Corsokoepel>

⁴ <https://www.immaterieelerfgoed.nl/en/sintmaartenvieringnutrecht> (accessed 25 May 2021).

⁵ <https://www.immaterieelerfgoed.nl/en/draakstekenbeesel> (accessed 25 May 2021).

some practitioners of intangible heritage lose their individuality or local colour? Do larger groups of practitioners tend to absorb smaller groups (Elpers, Verburg, 2020, 42)?

In our experience, ICH bearers sometimes have trouble finding each other. In order to foster exchange, we organise so-called face-to-face ICH Days in the Netherlands twice a year. Invited to join these events are the communities, groups, and individuals who are involved in an ICH practice inscribed in one of the three Dutch inventories⁶. Next to workshops on diverse ICH-related topics, the ICH Days offer plenty of time and a safe space for personal exchanges about the opportunities and challenges surrounding the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage.

Approaches that consider inventories as stimuli and infrastructures for social networks, rather than lists of single quantifiable elements of ICH (with which state parties tend to claim their successes in the cultural field (cf. Hafstein, 2012, 504)), like the one we have just explored, are effective because they emphasise the role of inventories as safeguarding tools.

2. Interactivity and the dynamics of intangible cultural heritage

Let us share a second thought: interactive inventories can significantly contribute to the development of approaches that are based on a dynamic, rather than fixed, understanding of heritage. These approaches are said to be dynamic because they recognise that cultural practices are constantly changing, that heritage items are often surrounded by a variety of different emotions and multiple perspectives (cf. Rana/Willemsen/Dibbits, 2017), and that heritage itself is an ongoing metacultural process of making and remaking heritage during which diverse actors are constantly negotiating its present and future meaning.

Roughly 70% of the participants who took part in the survey found it very important that an inventory should be updated and only 7% found this not or less important (graphic 2). Updates can, of course, be fostered by interactive inventories that allow ICH practitioners to integrate changes and developments concerning cultural practices and their safeguarding; a point which we come back to below. Additionally, interactive inventories can also engage more stakeholders than groups of practitioners alone and can stimulate dialogue and debate about heritage, which we see as central to democratic and inclusive heritage-making processes. However, they need good moderation and sound methods if they are to lead to fruitful results and mutual understanding (rather than confronting conflicts).

In the Netherlands, for instance, the method of "emotion networking" turns out to be highly appreciated, not only in the heritage field, but also on a much larger scale and in different parts of society. The method brings together and provides insights into complicated interplays between emotions, interests, and different sorts of knowledge about one particular heritage item.⁷ Another tool, developed by the Dutch Centre for Intangible Cultural Heritage, is a wheel chart that stimulates

⁶ A so-called "Network" which collects ICH in a Wikipedia-like way, a so-called "Inventory" on which ICH elements are listed for which the bearers have developed a safeguarding plan, and a "Register" with good practices of safeguarding. <https://www.immaterieelerfgoed.nl/en/netwerkinventarisregister> (accessed 25 May 2021).

⁷ <https://www.reinwardt.ahk.nl/en/research-group-cultural-heritage/emotion-networking/> (accessed 25 May 2021).

dialogue about what can be called "contested" ICH, i.e. heritage whose meaning and ownership is debated upon in society.⁸

Graphic 2 – Opinion: How should an ICH inventory be? (Variables 32)

There are no updates, no exchanges, no dialogues, and no debates without interactivity. However, that does not mean that interactivity should always be realised through digital methods and specifically interactive digital inventories. Experience tells us that people need small safe settings in which they can openly talk about challenges, share negative emotions, and discuss difficult topics. Digital interactivity should therefore be customised based on thorough case-by-case reflections.

3. Updated! Online!?

Back to the notion that inventories should be updated. There is no question that dynamic heritage should also be described on dynamic and regularly updated inventories,⁹ especially if those inventories also have an archival function - as 66% of the respondents find important (graphic 3) - and if the archived version of ICH is considered as the "right" one or the one that should be "protected". Updates on how ICH elements and their bearers change over time prevent processes of fossilisation. But what else should be updated? In the Netherlands, for instance, updates mostly concern the information about safeguarding measures of the inventory's diverse heritage items. The updates are based on evaluations carried out with the practitioners, which reflects on executed as well as planned safeguarding measures. The evaluations take place every three years.¹⁰

⁸ <https://www.immaterieelerfgoed.nl/en/page/9345/keuzekompas-ga-in-gesprek-over-immaterieel-erfgoed> (accessed 25 May 2021).

⁹ The phenomenon that heritage lists are considered and treated as heritage themselves that we have to care for (cf. Harrison 2020, 14).

¹⁰ The growing number of elements of ICH inscribed in the inventory is a challenge for the manageability of the evaluations.

Updates could, and in our eyes, should also include the impact of inventory measures on cultural practices and should describe the extent to which measures mitigate or amplify cultural change. This is a reflective feature that could also address the right of heritage practitioners to reject the inscription of an element in an inventory (cf. SIEF, 2021).

Another thought-provoking result of the survey that is visible in graphic 2 is the following: inventories should be (open access) online (more than 87% of the respondents find this important or very important). The issue of digitisation is complex and we would be interested in getting to know more about the details of the perceptions and expectations that lie behind this percentage. What exactly should be online and why? (See below)

One of the aspects of providing data online is that, beyond being linked to each other (cf. Sousa, 2018, 41), data sets can be compared to one another easily - sometimes too easily. This not only concerns information about the diverse ICH elements within one inventory but also information about ICH elements in different inventories or the inventories themselves. In order to avoid drawing misleading conclusions from such comparisons, it is of crucial importance that online inventories provide the visitor with enough contextual information regarding the heritage-making process which the inventory is part of. After all, each inventory is constructed within the confines of a specific heritage regime which comes with a particular understanding of how to implement the 2003 UNESCO Convention and how to put together inventories. These understandings might differ quite substantially from one inventory to the next, making comparisons much more complex than it seems at first sight.

Graphic 3 – Opinion: Why are ICH inventories important?

4. Safeguarding ICH and participation via the inventory

Graphic 3 shows that "to safeguard ICH" is considered to be the main purpose of inventories (more than 71% of the respondents find this aspect very important). However, the other elements mentioned in the graphic are also part of the safeguarding process. With this in mind, it is interesting to see which ones are considered more important than others. The elements of safeguarding that contribute to the creation of an informative inventory and increase the public visibility of intangible cultural heritage stand out the most. Engaging people, enhancing ICH, and increasing ICH practitioners, aspects that are all closely related to ICH bearers and that require interactivity and dialogue, are less valued. This resonates with the results presented in graphic 5 as it showed us that the main role of the bearers of intangible cultural heritage is seen as identifying ICH for the inventories and providing information on ICH. "To benefit from the inventory" is only in third place.¹¹ This leads us to ask certain questions: what is meant by "to safeguard ICH" precisely? For whom should it be safeguarded?

Depending on the way that application and inscription processes are organised and depending on how well the bearers of heritage participate in this process, the safeguarding function of inventories can already come into play long before an element of ICH is inscribed in an inventory. In the Netherlands, for instance, the writing of the application for the so-called "Inventaris" comes with an elaborate training, offered by the Dutch Centre for Intangible Cultural Heritage. During the training, the concept of ICH as well as the spirit of the Convention and corresponding safeguarding activities are presented and discussed. Heritage bearers are encouraged to think about the core elements and values of their heritage and are supported during the writing of their safeguarding plans. Next to this outcome, the main outcome might be that the bearers of ICH develop a (more) reflexive relationship with their ICH which is one of the preconditions of heritage (cf. Kirshenblatt-Gimblett, 2014) - and safeguarding.

Graphic 4 – Opinion: What is important in a participatory ICH inventory?

¹¹ It remains unclear what "benefit" precisely means and if financial or legal aspects might be implicated.

Graphic 5 – Opinion: What should be the role of communities, groups or individuals in ICH inventories?

Graphic 4 visualises which elements are seen as important in a participatory inventory. When considering this subject, we will only refer to the following issue: the different elements show the challenges and contradictions that lie within participatory practices. On the one hand, the respondents' answers reveal the desire to create an accessible environment for ICH practitioners to engage with, and on the other hand, they reflect the need for support and moderation. In the Netherlands this is a challenge as well. One of the Dutch inventories, called "Netwerk [Network]", works in a Wikipedia-like manner: practitioners can inscribe their ICH themselves. However, quite substantial misunderstandings of intangible cultural heritage and factually deficient descriptions of specific heritages sometimes occur. In other cases, things are described in inappropriate vocabulary in the sense of the UNESCO Convention or simply in bad Dutch. Consequently, thorough checks as well as detailed editing by heritage "experts", then take place. Are illusions of participation created (cf. Lynch, 2020, 13)? Or do such processes point to the necessity to protect the participants of a participatory project? Should moderation also take place if participation goes further, as is the case in graphic 5 where heritage bearers are assigned the role of organisers and promoters of the inventories as well as managers of the inventory process? In any case, we think that it is helpful to relinquish approaches to participation that are derived from the idea of different grades of involvement as described in hierarchies (cf. the concept of participation leader; Arnstein, 1969). The linear structure that the concept of participation leaders is based on is problematic because it does not take into account the dynamics of social reality and the need for flexibility. Furthermore, any level of participation other than the very highest could be seen as a failure, potentially leading to the delegitimisation of participation processes. In the case of ICH inventories, the challenge is to find a good balance between the participation of heritage practitioners and the work of experts (cf. Sousa, 2018, 33) and to keep the process of collaboration as dynamic as ICH is.

5. Final notes and other questions

Considering its main objective, the survey "Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH)" collected quantitative information mainly on the question of how inventories are currently used and structured. However, future investigations should look to bring additional information that will allow us to tease out correlations between different answers, leading to more detailed interpretations. Furthermore, qualitative data collected from interviews will allow us to complement the knowledge that has been produced and to respond to the clues and questions brought about by the survey results. This will help us to understand why and how the process of heritage-making and listing is made, considering, for instance, the question of the agency of inventories in relation to ICH safeguarding.

Regarding online and open access inventories, we consider that this theme can be explored in future research projects by raising some of the following questions: what precisely (of the aspects made visible in graphic 6) should be online and why? Should specific aspects also be prevented from going online and remain hidden? What about privacy? And what about so-called "clandestine heritage"? Do the bearers of heritage still feel "safe" when (the updates of) their safeguarding plans are done online, or do they perceive this as an alienating mechanism that leads to (social) control, as we have experienced in the Netherlands? Based on the data visualised in graphic 1 and 2, we assume that online inventories are considered to be important because they provide information to the public and promote interactivity, but is this public element seen as a value in itself? Or is it rather seen as a means to raise awareness and empower the bearers of the intangible cultural heritage?

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ANNEX A - SURVEY

Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage

The DIGITAL ICH Observatory is conducting a survey on Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH). With this survey we intend to study the practices and opinions of users of ICH inventories.

This survey refers to the different domains of ICH - oral expressions (legends, folk tales, traditional songs ...); arts and crafts; social practices, celebrations and rituals; performing arts (popular theatre, traditional dance...) and knowledge and practices related to nature and the universe.

This survey is anonymous. No information about your identity is asked. The data will only be used for statistical treatment. Estimated time to answer: less than 15 minutes.

***Required**

1. *

Tick all that apply.

I agree to participate and I will only reply once.

To make sure you are not a robot...

2. Type the characters you see above *

You, ICH & Inventories

3. Your relation with INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE (ICH) (choose 1 option, the one that best fits your situation) *

Mark only one oval.

- I practice traditions (crafts, dance, music, celebrations, traditional knowledge ...)
- I work on intangible cultural heritage
- I study on intangible cultural heritage
- I am curious and I like to know/see expressions of intangible cultural heritage
- I have an opinion on matters of intangible cultural heritage
- I am not related to intangible cultural heritage
- Other: _____

4. Your relation with INVENTORIES of intangible cultural heritage (ICH Inventories) (choose 1 option, the one that best fits your situation) *

Mark only one oval.

- I practice traditions that have been inventorying
- I work on inventories of intangible cultural heritage
- I study on inventories of intangible cultural heritage
- I am curious and I like to use inventories of intangible cultural heritage
- I have an opinion on matters of intangible cultural heritage
- I am not related to inventories of intangible cultural heritage
- Other: _____

5. Do you know the 2003 UNESCO CONVENTION for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage? *

Mark only one oval.

- I don't know
- I've heard about it
- I know badly
- I know
- I know very well

Skip to question 6

Socio & demographic characterization (1)

6. Country of residence *

Mark only one oval.

7. Age *

Mark only one oval.

- Up to 20 years
- 21 to 40 years
- 41 to 60 years
- 61 years or more

8. Sex *

Mark only one oval.

- Female
- Male

9. Residence area *

Mark only one oval.

Urban

Rural

10. Education *

Mark only one oval.

Primary school

High school

Academic degree (Associate, Bachelor, Master or Doctoral)

Other: _____

11. Current occupation *

Mark only one oval.

Employee

Independent worker

Student

Retired

Unemployed

Other: _____

Socio & demographic characterization (2)

12. Your work sector (choose 1 option) *

Mark only one oval.

- I'm not working
- Industry
- Agriculture
- Trade
- Education, science or culture
- Public administration
- Other Services

13. Your professional group (choose 1 option) *

Mark only one oval.

- I'm not working
- Entrepreneur
- Intellectual and scientific specialist
- Administrative
- Technical or operational worker
- Unqualified

14. Entity where you work (choose 1 option) *

Mark only one oval.

- I'm not working
- Private company
- State - National Administration
- State - Regional or local administration
- NGO
- University or Research Center
- Other: _____

Your practice & ICH inventories (1)

15. How many inventories of intangible cultural heritage (ICH inventories) have you consulted? *

Mark only one oval.

- none
- 1
- 2 to 4
- 5 to 7
- 8 to 10
- more than 10

Your practice & ICH inventories (2)

16. How often do you check ICH inventories? *

Mark only one oval.

- Every day
- At least once a week
- At least once a month
- At least once a year
- I haven't used for years

17. In normal access, how much time do you spend on an ICH inventory? *

Mark only one oval.

- Up to 5 minutes
- Up to 15 minutes
- Up to 30 minutes
- Up to 1 hour
- More than 1 hour

18. Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are in what language? *

Mark only one oval.

- In my country's language
- English
- In another Language

19. Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are: *

Mark only one oval.

- Transnational
- National
- Regional
- Local

Your practice & ICH inventories (3)

20. Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are about (choose 1 option): *

Mark only one oval.

- Oral traditions and expressions
- Performing arts
- Social practices, rituals and festive events
- Knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe
- Traditional craftsmanship
- All the domains mentioned above

21. On average, how many traditions are inscribed in the ICH Inventories you consult? *

Mark only one oval.

- up to 10
- 10 to 50
- 50 to 100
- more than 100
- I don't know

22. Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are promoted by: (choose 1 option) *

Mark only one oval.

- Private company
- State - National Administration
- State - Regional or local administration
- ICH practitioners, NGOs, local associations, individuals or other informal groups
- University or Research Center
- UNESCO Organization
- I don't know
- Other: _____

23. Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are: *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes	No	I don't know
Online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Open access	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Public	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Updated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have a call for participation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Your practice & Usability

24. When I use an ICH Inventory: (choose the frequency by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Many times	Always
I visit only the front page	<input type="radio"/>				
I explore multiple pages	<input type="radio"/>				
I know what I'm looking for	<input type="radio"/>				
I explore by menu	<input type="radio"/>				
I explore by links	<input type="radio"/>				
I explore by search	<input type="radio"/>				

25. When I explore contents in an ICH Inventory: (choose the frequency by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Many times	Always
I read texts	<input type="radio"/>				
I watch videos	<input type="radio"/>				
I listen to soundtracks	<input type="radio"/>				
I look at photos	<input type="radio"/>				

26. About social media, in an ICH Inventory: (choose the frequency by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Many times	Always
I use their social media	<input type="radio"/>				
I share info on my social media	<input type="radio"/>				

Your practice & Search

27. When I search in an ICH Inventory: (choose the frequency by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Many times	Always
I use simple search	<input type="radio"/>				
I use advanced search	<input type="radio"/>				
I search by location	<input type="radio"/>				
I search by ICH domain	<input type="radio"/>				
I search by keyword	<input type="radio"/>				

Your practice & Participation

28. About participation, in an ICH inventory: (choose the frequency by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Many times	Always
I leave comments	<input type="radio"/>				
I participate in forums	<input type="radio"/>				
I contact for questions	<input type="radio"/>				
I participate with contents	<input type="radio"/>				
I subscribe to "communities"	<input type="radio"/>				
I subscribe to newsletters	<input type="radio"/>				

29.

Have you ever participated in an ICH Inventory? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes	No
Participating in public sessions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participating in plenaries or assemblies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participating in debates	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participating in capacity-building/Workshops	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Your opinion & Importance (3)

34. What information should be available in an ICH inventory? (choose the importance by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not Important	Less important	So-so	Important	Very important
Tradition name	<input type="radio"/>				
Practitioners info	<input type="radio"/>				
Short description of the tradition	<input type="radio"/>				
Detailed Description of the tradition	<input type="radio"/>				
ICH History	<input type="radio"/>				
ICH Threats	<input type="radio"/>				
Safeguard plan	<input type="radio"/>				
Videos	<input type="radio"/>				
Sounds	<input type="radio"/>				
Usual photos	<input type="radio"/>				
360° photos	<input type="radio"/>				
Streaming sessions	<input type="radio"/>				
Access to Virtual Reality/Augmented Reality	<input type="radio"/>				
Methodology/team info	<input type="radio"/>				
Community consent	<input type="radio"/>				
Mention UNESCO Convention	<input type="radio"/>				
Intellectual rights	<input type="radio"/>				

36. What is important in a participatory ICH inventory? (choose the importance by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not Important	Less important	So-so	Important	Very important	No opinion
To allow voluntary contributions	<input type="radio"/>					
To have a call for contributions	<input type="radio"/>					
To give instructions for contributions	<input type="radio"/>					
To be easy to fill in	<input type="radio"/>					
To have moderators	<input type="radio"/>					
To provide technical support	<input type="radio"/>					
To use participatory techniques	<input type="radio"/>					

The survey ended. Please submit. Thank you for your participation.

37. Control question - Is this the 1st time you answer this survey? *

Tick all that apply.

Yes

No

38. How do you evaluate the fulfillment of this survey? (choose 1 option)

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very difficult	<input type="radio"/>	Very easy				

39. Comments

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Google Forms

ANNEX B - All variables

Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage - Survey

Frequency tables and percentages in SPSS

(Portuguese version)

Tabela de Frequências

Relation to ICH

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	I practice ICH	35	14,2	14,2	14,2
	I work or study on ICH	192	78,0	78,0	92,3
	I am curious on ICH	19	7,7	7,7	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Relation with ICH Inventories

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	I practice ICH that have been inventorying	19	7,7	7,7	7,7
	I work or study on ICH inventories	182	74,0	74,0	81,7
	I am curious on ICH inventories	45	18,3	18,3	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Do you know the 2003 UNESCO CONVENTION?

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	I don't know or badly know	49	19,9	19,9	19,9
	I know well or very well	197	80,1	80,1	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Country of residence

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Albania	1	,4	,4	,4
	Argentina	1	,4	,4	,8
	Armenia	2	,8	,8	1,6
	Australia	1	,4	,4	2,0
	Austria	2	,8	,8	2,8
	Belarus	1	,4	,4	3,3
	Belgium	9	3,7	3,7	6,9
	Belize	1	,4	,4	7,3
	Benin	1	,4	,4	7,7
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	1	,4	,4	8,1
	Brazil	3	1,2	1,2	9,3
	Bulgaria	2	,8	,8	10,2
	Burma	1	,4	,4	10,6
	Canada	7	2,8	2,8	13,4
	Central African Republic	2	,8	,8	14,2
	Colombia	4	1,6	1,6	15,9
	Cote d'Ivoire	1	,4	,4	16,3
	Croatia	3	1,2	1,2	17,5
	Czech Republic	3	1,2	1,2	18,7
	Dominican Republic	1	,4	,4	19,1
	Egypt	1	,4	,4	19,5
	Estonia	1	,4	,4	19,9
	Faroe Islands	1	,4	,4	20,3
	Fiji	1	,4	,4	20,7
	Finland	3	1,2	1,2	22,0
	France	18	7,3	7,3	29,3
	French Guiana	1	,4	,4	29,7
	Georgia	1	,4	,4	30,1
	Germany	4	1,6	1,6	31,7
	Ghana	1	,4	,4	32,1

Country of residence

	Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Greece	1	,4	,4	32,5
Greenland	1	,4	,4	32,9
India	5	2,0	2,0	35,0
Indonesia	1	,4	,4	35,4
Iraq	1	,4	,4	35,8
Ireland	29	11,8	11,8	47,6
Italy	7	2,8	2,8	50,4
Jamaica	1	,4	,4	50,8
Japan	1	,4	,4	51,2
Korea, South	2	,8	,8	52,0
Kyrgyzstan	3	1,2	1,2	53,3
Latvia	2	,8	,8	54,1
Lithuania	17	6,9	6,9	61,0
Malawi	1	,4	,4	61,4
Malaysia	1	,4	,4	61,8
Mauritius	2	,8	,8	62,6
Mayotte	1	,4	,4	63,0
Mexico	2	,8	,8	63,8
Mongolia	1	,4	,4	64,2
Montenegro	1	,4	,4	64,6
Morocco	2	,8	,8	65,4
Nepal	2	,8	,8	66,3
Netherlands	2	,8	,8	67,1
Netherlands Antilles	1	,4	,4	67,5
Nigeria	4	1,6	1,6	69,1
Norway	3	1,2	1,2	70,3
Paraguay	1	,4	,4	70,7
Poland	3	1,2	1,2	72,0
Portugal	15	6,1	6,1	78,0
Romania	1	,4	,4	78,5
Russia	1	,4	,4	78,9
Saint Lucia	1	,4	,4	79,3
Samoa	1	,4	,4	79,7
Serbia	2	,8	,8	80,5
Singapore	1	,4	,4	80,9
Slovenia	5	2,0	2,0	82,9
Spain	12	4,9	4,9	87,8
Sri Lanka	1	,4	,4	88,2

Country of residence

	Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Swaziland	1	,4	,4	88,6
Sweden	5	2,0	2,0	90,7
Switzerland	1	,4	,4	91,1
Thailand	8	3,3	3,3	94,3
Tonga	1	,4	,4	94,7
Tunisia	1	,4	,4	95,1
Turkmenistan	1	,4	,4	95,5
Uganda	1	,4	,4	95,9
Ukraine	2	,8	,8	96,7
United Kingdom	2	,8	,8	97,6
United States	3	1,2	1,2	98,8
Yemen	1	,4	,4	99,2
Zambia	1	,4	,4	99,6
Zimbabwe	1	,4	,4	100,0
Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Region

	Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido Africa	19	7,7	7,7	7,7
Arab States	4	1,6	1,6	9,3
Asia and the Pacific	33	13,4	13,4	22,8
Europe and North America	174	70,7	70,7	93,5
Latin America and the Caribbean	16	6,5	6,5	100,0
Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Age

	Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido 21 to 40 years	69	28,0	28,0	28,0
41 to 60 years	135	54,9	54,9	82,9
61 years or more	42	17,1	17,1	100,0
Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Sex

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Female	152	61,8	61,8	61,8
	Male	94	38,2	38,2	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Residence area

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Rural	71	28,9	28,9	28,9
	Urban	175	71,1	71,1	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Education

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Academic degree (Associate, Bachelor, Master or Doctoral)	236	95,9	95,9	95,9
	High school	10	4,1	4,1	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Occupation

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Employee	215	87,4	87,4	87,4
	Student	10	4,1	4,1	91,5
	Retired	20	8,1	8,1	99,6
	Unemployed	1	,4	,4	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Work Sector

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Industry	3	1,2	1,3	1,3
	Agriculture	2	,8	,9	2,2
	Education, science or culture	172	69,9	74,5	76,6
	Trade	2	,8	,9	77,5
	Public administration	33	13,4	14,3	91,8
	Other Services	19	7,7	8,2	100,0
	Total	231	93,9	100,0	
Omisso	0	15	6,1		
Total		246	100,0		

Profession

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Entrepreneur	11	4,5	4,7	4,7
	Intellectual and scientific specialist	153	62,2	65,1	69,8
	Administrative	45	18,3	19,1	88,9
	Technical or operational worker	25	10,2	10,6	99,6
	Unqualified	1	,4	,4	100,0
	Total	235	95,5	100,0	
Omisso	0	11	4,5		
Total		246	100,0		

Entety

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Private company	28	11,4	12,1	12,1
	State - National Administration	59	24,0	25,4	37,5
	State - Regional or local administration	39	15,9	16,8	54,3
	NGO	50	20,3	21,6	75,9
	University or Research Center	56	22,8	24,1	100,0
	Total	232	94,3	100,0	
Omisso	0	14	5,7		
Total		246	100,0		

How many inventories of intangible cultural heritage (ICH inventories) have you consulted?

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	none	30	12,2	12,2	12,2
	one	33	13,4	13,4	25,6
	2 to 4	71	28,9	28,9	54,5
	5 to 7	23	9,3	9,3	63,8
	8 to 10	16	6,5	6,5	70,3
	more than 10	73	29,7	29,7	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

How often do you check ICH inventories?

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Every day	24	9,8	11,1	11,1
	At least once a week	43	17,5	19,9	31,0
	At least once a month	77	31,3	35,6	66,7
	At least once a year	67	27,2	31,0	97,7
	I haven't used for years	5	2,0	2,3	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

In normal access, how much time do you spend on an ICH inventory?

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Up to 5 minutes	10	4,1	4,6	4,6
	Up to 15 minutes	45	18,3	20,8	25,5
	Up to 30 minutes	63	25,6	29,2	54,6
	Up to 1 hour	40	16,3	18,5	73,1
	More than 1 hour	58	23,6	26,9	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are in what language?

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	In my country's language	120	48,8	55,6	55,6
	English	89	36,2	41,2	96,8
	In another Language	7	2,8	3,2	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are:

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Transnational	43	17,5	19,9	19,9
	National	120	48,8	55,6	75,5
	Regional	37	15,0	17,1	92,6
	Local	16	6,5	7,4	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are about (choose 1 option):

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Oral traditions and expressions	19	7,7	8,8	8,8
	Performing arts	19	7,7	8,8	17,6
	Social practices, rituals and festive events	33	13,4	15,3	32,9
	Knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe	7	2,8	3,2	36,1
	Traditional craftsmanship	24	9,8	11,1	47,2
	All the domains mentioned above	114	46,3	52,8	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

On average, how many traditions are inscribed in the ICH Inventories you consult?

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	up to 10	53	21,5	25,2	25,2
	10 to 50	58	23,6	27,6	52,9
	50 to 100	24	9,8	11,4	64,3
	more than 100	35	14,2	16,7	81,0
	I don't know	40	16,3	19,0	100,0
	Total	210	85,4	100,0	
Omisso	0	36	14,6		
Total		246	100,0		

Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are promoted by: (choose 1 option)

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Private company	1	,4	,5	,5
	State - National Administration	75	30,5	34,7	35,2
	State - Regional or local administration	31	12,6	14,4	49,5
	ICH practitioners, NGOs, local associations, individuals or other informal groups	56	22,8	25,9	75,5
	University or Research Center	13	5,3	6,0	81,5
	UNESCO Organization	29	11,8	13,4	94,9
	I don't know	10	4,1	4,6	99,5
	Others	1	,4	,5	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are: [Online]

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Yes	172	69,9	79,6	79,6
	No	38	15,4	17,6	97,2
	I don't know	6	2,4	2,8	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are: [Open access]

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Yes	158	64,2	73,1	73,1
	No	36	14,6	16,7	89,8
	I don't know	22	8,9	10,2	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are: [Public]

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Yes	188	76,4	87,0	87,0
	No	23	9,3	10,6	97,7
	I don't know	5	2,0	2,3	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are: [Updated]

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Yes	116	47,2	53,7	53,7
	No	37	15,0	17,1	70,8
	I don't know	63	25,6	29,2	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are: [Have a call for participation]

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Yes	92	37,4	42,6	42,6
	No	70	28,5	32,4	75,0
	I don't know	54	22,0	25,0	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

FirstPage3

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	85	34,6	39,4	39,4
	Sometimes	85	34,6	39,4	78,7
	Many times or always	46	18,7	21,3	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

multiple pages

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	12	4,9	5,6	5,6
	Sometimes	58	23,6	26,9	32,4
	Many times or always	146	59,3	67,6	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

know what I'm looking

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	13	5,3	6,0	6,0
	Sometimes	67	27,2	31,0	37,0
	Many times or always	136	55,3	63,0	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

explore by menu

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	20	8,1	9,3	9,3
	Sometimes	79	32,1	36,6	45,8
	Many times or always	117	47,6	54,2	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

explore by links

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	40	16,3	18,5	18,5
	Sometimes	95	38,6	44,0	62,5
	Many times or always	81	32,9	37,5	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

explore by search

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	23	9,3	10,6	10,6
	Sometimes	75	30,5	34,7	45,4
	Many times or always	118	48,0	54,6	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

read texts

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	7	2,8	3,2	3,2
	Sometimes	51	20,7	23,6	26,9
	Many times or always	158	64,2	73,1	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

watch videos

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	32	13,0	14,8	14,8
	Sometimes	83	33,7	38,4	53,2
	Many times or always	101	41,1	46,8	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

listen to soundtracks

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	79	32,1	36,6	36,6
	Sometimes	70	28,5	32,4	69,0
	Many times or always	67	27,2	31,0	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

look at photos

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	6	2,4	2,8	2,8
	Sometimes	52	21,1	24,1	26,9
	Many times or always	158	64,2	73,1	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

I use their social media

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	87	35,4	40,3	40,3
	Sometimes	72	29,3	33,3	73,6
	Many times or always	57	23,2	26,4	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

share info on my social media

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	112	45,5	51,9	51,9
	Sometimes	64	26,0	29,6	81,5
	Many times or always	40	16,3	18,5	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

simple search

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	17	6,9	7,9	7,9
	Sometimes	79	32,1	36,6	44,4
	Many times or always	120	48,8	55,6	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

advanced search

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	57	23,2	26,4	26,4
	Sometimes	88	35,8	40,7	67,1
	Many times or always	71	28,9	32,9	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

search by location

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	32	13,0	14,8	14,8
	Sometimes	90	36,6	41,7	56,5
	Many times or always	94	38,2	43,5	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

search by ICH domain

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	49	19,9	22,7	22,7
	Sometimes	71	28,9	32,9	55,6
	Many times or always	96	39,0	44,4	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

I search by keyword

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	23	9,3	10,6	10,6
	Sometimes	71	28,9	32,9	43,5
	Many times or always	122	49,6	56,5	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

leave comments

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	154	62,6	71,3	71,3
	Sometimes	45	18,3	20,8	92,1
	Many times or always	17	6,9	7,9	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

participate in forums

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	152	61,8	70,4	70,4
	Sometimes	44	17,9	20,4	90,7
	Many times or always	20	8,1	9,3	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

contact for questions

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	122	49,6	56,5	56,5
	Sometimes	65	26,4	30,1	86,6
	Many times or always	29	11,8	13,4	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

participate with contents

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	115	46,7	53,2	53,2
	Sometimes	61	24,8	28,2	81,5
	Many times or always	40	16,3	18,5	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

subscribe to "communities"

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	137	55,7	63,4	63,4
	Sometimes	46	18,7	21,3	84,7
	Many times or always	33	13,4	15,3	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

subscribe to newsletters

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Never or rarely	100	40,7	46,3	46,3
	Sometimes	74	30,1	34,3	80,6
	Many times or always	42	17,1	19,4	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

To enhance ICH

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	28	11,4	13,1	13,1
	Important	70	28,5	32,7	45,8
	Very important	116	47,2	54,2	100,0
	Total	214	87,0	100,0	
Omisso	0	2	,8		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	32	13,0		
Total		246	100,0		

To provide info

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	5	2,0	2,4	2,4
	Important	57	23,2	26,9	29,2
	Very important	150	61,0	70,8	100,0
	Total	212	86,2	100,0	
Omisso	0	4	1,6		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	34	13,8		
Total		246	100,0		

To archive ICH

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	18	7,3	8,5	8,5
	Important	53	21,5	25,0	33,5
	Very important	141	57,3	66,5	100,0
	Total	212	86,2	100,0	
Omisso	0	4	1,6		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	34	13,8		
Total		246	100,0		

To give ICH visibility

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	12	4,9	5,8	5,8
	Important	49	19,9	23,7	29,5
	Very important	146	59,3	70,5	100,0
	Total	207	84,1	100,0	
Omisso	0	9	3,7		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	39	15,9		
Total		246	100,0		

To enjoy ICH

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	50	20,3	23,9	23,9
	Important	77	31,3	36,8	60,8
	Very important	82	33,3	39,2	100,0
	Total	209	85,0	100,0	
Omisso	0	7	2,8		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	37	15,0		
Total		246	100,0		

To safeguard ICH

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	13	5,3	6,3	6,3
	Important	46	18,7	22,1	28,4
	Very important	149	60,6	71,6	100,0
	Total	208	84,6	100,0	
Omisso	0	8	3,3		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	38	15,4		
Total		246	100,0		

Engage people with ICH

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	26	10,6	12,5	12,5
	Important	63	25,6	30,3	42,8
	Very important	119	48,4	57,2	100,0
	Total	208	84,6	100,0	
Omisso	0	8	3,3		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	38	15,4		
Total		246	100,0		

To increase ICH practitioners

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	47	19,1	22,7	22,7
	Important	57	23,2	27,5	50,2
	Very important	103	41,9	49,8	100,0
	Total	207	84,1	100,0	
Omisso	0	9	3,7		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	39	15,9		
Total		246	100,0		

Scientific

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	71	28,9	34,0	34,0
	Important	72	29,3	34,4	68,4
	Very important	66	26,8	31,6	100,0
	Total	209	85,0	100,0	
Omisso	0	7	2,8		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	37	15,0		
Total		246	100,0		

Public

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	13	5,3	6,1	6,1
	Important	47	19,1	22,1	28,2
	Very important	153	62,2	71,8	100,0
	Total	213	86,6	100,0	
Omisso	0	3	1,2		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	33	13,4		
Total		246	100,0		

Interactive

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	51	20,7	24,2	24,2
	Important	68	27,6	32,2	56,4
	Very important	92	37,4	43,6	100,0
	Total	211	85,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	5	2,0		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	35	14,2		
Total		246	100,0		

online

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	28	11,4	13,1	13,1
	Important	59	24,0	27,6	40,7
	Very important	127	51,6	59,3	100,0
	Total	214	87,0	100,0	
Omisso	0	2	,8		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	32	13,0		
Total		246	100,0		

Funny

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	154	62,6	75,5	75,5
	Important	32	13,0	15,7	91,2
	Very important	18	7,3	8,8	100,0
	Total	204	82,9	100,0	
Omisso	0	12	4,9		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	42	17,1		
Total		246	100,0		

Searchable

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	18	7,3	8,5	8,5
	Important	59	24,0	28,0	36,5
	Very important	134	54,5	63,5	100,0
	Total	211	85,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	5	2,0		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	35	14,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Updated

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	14	5,7	6,8	6,8
	Important	48	19,5	23,4	30,2
	Very important	143	58,1	69,8	100,0
	Total	205	83,3	100,0	
Omisso	0	11	4,5		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	41	16,7		
Total		246	100,0		

Anappealingdesign

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	42	17,1	19,6	19,6
	Important	98	39,8	45,8	65,4
	Very important	74	30,1	34,6	100,0
	Total	214	87,0	100,0	
Omisso	0	2	,8		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	32	13,0		
Total		246	100,0		

ClearMenus

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	20	8,1	9,4	9,4
	Important	75	30,5	35,2	44,6
	Very important	118	48,0	55,4	100,0
	Total	213	86,6	100,0	
Omisso	0	3	1,2		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	33	13,4		
Total		246	100,0		

Forums

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	74	30,1	35,1	35,1
	Important	75	30,5	35,5	70,6
	Very important	62	25,2	29,4	100,0
	Total	211	85,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	5	2,0		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	35	14,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Contentstoshare

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	33	13,4	15,3	15,3
	Important	100	40,7	46,5	61,9
	Very important	82	33,3	38,1	100,0
	Total	215	87,4	100,0	
Omisso	0	1	,4		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	31	12,6		
Total		246	100,0		

presenceonsocialnetworks

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	58	23,6	27,5	27,5
	Important	83	33,7	39,3	66,8
	Very important	70	28,5	33,2	100,0
	Total	211	85,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	5	2,0		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	35	14,2		
Total		246	100,0		

ANewsletter

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	91	37,0	42,7	42,7
	Important	76	30,9	35,7	78,4
	Very important	46	18,7	21,6	100,0
	Total	213	86,6	100,0	
Omisso	0	3	1,2		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	33	13,4		
Total		246	100,0		

mention the UNESCO 2003 Convention

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	45	18,3	21,3	21,3
	Important	80	32,5	37,9	59,2
	Very important	86	35,0	40,8	100,0
	Total	211	85,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	5	2,0		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	35	14,2		
Total		246	100,0		

To protect intellectual rights

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	26	10,6	12,4	12,4
	Important	64	26,0	30,6	43,1
	Very important	119	48,4	56,9	100,0
	Total	209	85,0	100,0	
Omisso	0	7	2,8		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	37	15,0		
Total		246	100,0		

Tradition name

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	6	2,4	2,8	2,8
	Important	69	28,0	31,9	34,7
	Very important	141	57,3	65,3	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Practitioners info

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	16	6,5	7,4	7,4
	Important	99	40,2	45,8	53,2
	Very important	101	41,1	46,8	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Short description of the tradition

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	7	2,8	3,2	3,2
	Important	76	30,9	35,2	38,4
	Very important	133	54,1	61,6	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Detailed Description of the tradition

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	38	15,4	17,6	17,6
	Important	94	38,2	43,5	61,1
	Very important	84	34,1	38,9	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

ICH History

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	47	19,1	21,8	21,8
	Important	102	41,5	47,2	69,0
	Very important	67	27,2	31,0	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

ICH Threats

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	43	17,5	19,9	19,9
	Important	104	42,3	48,1	68,1
	Very important	69	28,0	31,9	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Safeguard plan

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	35	14,2	16,2	16,2
	Important	96	39,0	44,4	60,6
	Very important	85	34,6	39,4	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Videos

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	40	16,3	18,5	18,5
	Important	98	39,8	45,4	63,9
	Very important	78	31,7	36,1	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Sounds

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	63	25,6	29,2	29,2
	Important	96	39,0	44,4	73,6
	Very important	57	23,2	26,4	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Usual Photos

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	20	8,1	9,3	9,3
	Important	104	42,3	48,1	57,4
	Very important	92	37,4	42,6	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

360° photos

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	142	57,7	65,7	65,7
	Important	42	17,1	19,4	85,2
	Very important	32	13,0	14,8	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Streaming Sessions

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	132	53,7	61,1	61,1
	Important	60	24,4	27,8	88,9
	Very important	24	9,8	11,1	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Access to Virtual Reality/Augmented Reality

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	145	58,9	67,1	67,1
	Important	51	20,7	23,6	90,7
	Very important	20	8,1	9,3	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Methodology/team info

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	72	29,3	33,3	33,3
	Important	95	38,6	44,0	77,3
	Very important	49	19,9	22,7	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Community consent

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	35	14,2	16,2	16,2
	Important	70	28,5	32,4	48,6
	Very important	111	45,1	51,4	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

To benefit from inventory

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	19	7,7	9,0	9,0
	Important	74	30,1	34,9	43,9
	Very important	119	48,4	56,1	100,0
	Total	212	86,2	100,0	
Omisso	0	4	1,6		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	34	13,8		
Total		246	100,0		

identify ICH to inventory

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	11	4,5	5,3	5,3
	Important	66	26,8	31,7	37,0
	Very important	131	53,3	63,0	100,0
	Total	208	84,6	100,0	
Omisso	0	8	3,3		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	38	15,4		
Total		246	100,0		

To inform on ICH

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	11	4,5	5,2	5,2
	Important	77	31,3	36,3	41,5
	Very important	124	50,4	58,5	100,0
	Total	212	86,2	100,0	
Omisso	0	4	1,6		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	34	13,8		
Total		246	100,0		

To advise on how to inventory

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	45	18,3	21,3	21,3
	Important	83	33,7	39,3	60,7
	Very important	83	33,7	39,3	100,0
	Total	211	85,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	5	2,0		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	35	14,2		
Total		246	100,0		

To be the promoter of the inventory

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	28	11,4	13,3	13,3
	Important	92	37,4	43,8	57,1
	Very important	90	36,6	42,9	100,0
	Total	210	85,4	100,0	
Omisso	0	6	2,4		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	36	14,6		
Total		246	100,0		

To decide what and how to inventory

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	48	19,5	23,0	23,0
	Important	68	27,6	32,5	55,5
	Very important	93	37,8	44,5	100,0
	Total	209	85,0	100,0	
Omisso	0	7	2,8		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	37	15,0		
Total		246	100,0		

To manage the inventory process

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	69	28,0	33,0	33,0
	Important	75	30,5	35,9	68,9
	Very important	65	26,4	31,1	100,0
	Total	209	85,0	100,0	
Omisso	0	7	2,8		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	37	15,0		
Total		246	100,0		

Voluntary contributions

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	37	15,0	17,4	17,4
	Important	89	36,2	41,8	59,2
	Very important	87	35,4	40,8	100,0
	Total	213	86,6	100,0	
Omisso	0	3	1,2		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	33	13,4		
Total		246	100,0		

Have a call

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	38	15,4	17,8	17,8
	Important	89	36,2	41,8	59,6
	Very important	86	35,0	40,4	100,0
	Total	213	86,6	100,0	
Omisso	0	3	1,2		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	33	13,4		
Total		246	100,0		

To give instructions for contributions

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	39	15,9	18,5	18,5
	Important	90	36,6	42,7	61,1
	Very important	82	33,3	38,9	100,0
	Total	211	85,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	5	2,0		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	35	14,2		
Total		246	100,0		

To be easy to fill

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	20	8,1	9,5	9,5
	Important	72	29,3	34,1	43,6
	Very important	119	48,4	56,4	100,0
	Total	211	85,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	5	2,0		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	35	14,2		
Total		246	100,0		

To have moderators

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	39	15,9	18,4	18,4
	Important	91	37,0	42,9	61,3
	Very important	82	33,3	38,7	100,0
	Total	212	86,2	100,0	
Omisso	0	4	1,6		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	34	13,8		
Total		246	100,0		

To provide technical support

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	15	6,1	7,0	7,0
	Important	85	34,6	39,9	46,9
	Very important	113	45,9	53,1	100,0
	Total	213	86,6	100,0	
Omisso	0	3	1,2		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	33	13,4		
Total		246	100,0		

To use participatory techniques

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Not Important or less important	20	8,1	9,5	9,5
	Important	77	31,3	36,7	46,2
	Very important	113	45,9	53,8	100,0
	Total	210	85,4	100,0	
Omisso	0	6	2,4		
	Sistema	30	12,2		
	Total	36	14,6		
Total		246	100,0		

Relation to ICH

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	I practice ICH + I am curious about ICH	54	22,0	22,0	22,0
	I work or study on ICH	192	78,0	78,0	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Region

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Europe and North America	174	70,7	70,7	70,7
	Other Regions	72	29,3	29,3	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Relation with ICH Inventories

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	I practice ICH inventoried	64	26,0	26,0	26,0
	I work or study on ICH inventories	182	74,0	74,0	100,0
	Total	246	100,0	100,0	

Have you ever participated in an ICH Inventory? [Participating in public sessions]

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	No	61	24,8	28,2	28,2
	Yes	155	63,0	71,8	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Have you ever participated in an ICH Inventory? [Participating in plenaries or assemblies]

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	No	79	32,1	36,6	36,6
	Yes	137	55,7	63,4	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Have you ever participated in an ICH Inventory? [Participating in juries/citizen panels]

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	No	128	52,0	59,3	59,3
	Yes	88	35,8	40,7	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Have you ever participated in an ICH Inventory? [Participating in debates]

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	No	93	37,8	43,1	43,1
	Yes	123	50,0	56,9	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

Have you ever participated in an ICH Inventory? [Participating in capacity-building/Workshops]

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	No	62	25,2	28,7	28,7
	Yes	154	62,6	71,3	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	0	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		

How do you evaluate the fulfillment of this survey? (choose 1 option)

		Frequência	Porcentagem	Porcentagem válida	Porcentagem acumulativa
Válido	Very Difficult	3	1,2	1,4	1,4
	Difficult	12	4,9	5,6	6,9
	So-so	60	24,4	27,8	34,7
	Easy	70	28,5	32,4	67,1
	Very Easy	71	28,9	32,9	100,0
	Total	216	87,8	100,0	
Omisso	Sistema	30	12,2		
Total		246	100,0		